

How can ChatGPT Support Teachers and Students in Vietnamese Civic Education

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Abstract: *The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies has presented new opportunities to enhance education across various subjects, including Civic Education. In the context of Vietnamese high schools, the integration of AI language models like ChatGPT can provide valuable support to both teachers and students in their learning journey. This paper explores the potential benefits of using ChatGPT as a supplementary tool to promote interactive learning, foster critical thinking, and facilitate access to relevant resources in Vietnamese Civic Education.*

Keywords: ChatGPT, civic education teaching, civic education learning, artificial intelligence, Vietnamese curriculum.

I. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become an essential part of everyday life. AI applications, such as voice assistants and smart speakers, are increasingly popular and widely used for simple tasks. For example, voice assistants like Amazon Alexa and Google Home can be used to play music, set alarms, and control smart home devices. Smart speakers like the Amazon Echo and Google Home Pod can also be used to get news and weather updates, answer questions, and even make phone calls. In addition to voice assistants and smart speakers, AI chatbots are also becoming more popular. AI chatbots are computer programs that can simulate conversation with humans. They are often used in customer service applications, where they can answer questions and resolve issues without the need for human intervention. AI chatbots are also being used in other areas, such as education and healthcare. For

example, AI chatbots can be used to provide personalized learning experiences or to help patients manage their health conditions. One of the most advanced AI chatbots is ChatGPT, a large language model chatbot developed by OpenAI. It is trained on a massive dataset of text and code, which allows it to generate human-like text and perform a variety of tasks. ChatGPT has been used for a variety of purposes, including writing scripts, translating languages, and even creating art. The use of AI in everyday life is still in its early stages, but it is growing rapidly. As AI technology continues to develop, we can expect to see even more innovative and useful applications of AI in our lives, when its abilities tend toward human-level [1].

The online education landscape in Vietnam has been experiencing rapid growth, witnessing an expansion of platforms and applications that facilitate

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remote teaching and learning. However, despite this progress, several challenges persist, requiring attention to optimize the learning experience for students and streamline the teaching process. One promising avenue is the integration of chatbots into online learning systems. Thanh et al. [2] conducted research wherein they proposed an online learning platform featuring a Vietnamese Virtual Assistant designed to support instructors in delivering lectures and assessing students' performance. In their approach, lecture content is presented through slides in PDF format, augmented with synthesized speech and facial expressions of the instructor, obtained from text inputs [3]. Another notable endeavor in chatbot development was undertaken by Trang et al. [4], wherein they utilized the Rasa framework to construct a chatbot. They introduced a custom pipeline for the Natural Language Understanding (NLU) model, incorporating pretrained language models, such as FastText and BERT, along with a tailor-made tokenizer. The application of pretrained language models to the NLU model demonstrated superior performance compared to training from scratch. Furthermore, Trang et al. [5] pursued the creation of a Vietnamese chatbot based on a seq2seq model coupled with an attention mechanism. Although this model was developed using a limited dataset, it successfully generated responses for users. Nevertheless, refinement is necessary to enhance the quality of the generated responses and achieve more meaningful conversations. In light of the growing potential of chatbots in online education, the previous research offer valuable insights and methodologies for developing effective chatbot-based learning systems in the Vietnamese context. The utilization of virtual assistants and custom pipelines incorporating pretrained language models exemplifies promising steps towards enhancing the overall educational

experience and fostering more interactive and dynamic online learning environments. As researchers continue to address challenges and explore innovative solutions, the integration of chatbots in the online education landscape has the potential to revolutionize the way students and instructors engage with educational content and assessments in Vietnam.

In recent research, several studies have been conducted to explore the role of ChatGPT in Vietnamese education, shedding light on its potential contributions to administrators, teachers, and students. These research efforts have delved into various aspects of integrating ChatGPT in educational settings, aiming to uncover the benefits and implications of AI-driven technologies in the Vietnamese context. The research conducted by Hana et al. [6], [7], [8] encompasses several studies that delve into the role of ChatGPT in Vietnamese education. These studies aim to uncover the potential contributions of ChatGPT to various stakeholders, including administrators, teachers, and students, within the educational landscape of Vietnam.

In a comprehensive series of studies conducted by Quy et al. [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], the performance of ChatGPT was rigorously evaluated on the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination. This examination encompasses a wide range of subjects, including mathematics, literature, English, physics, chemistry, biology, history, geography, and civic education. The research findings demonstrate that ChatGPT exhibits a general proficiency in the examination, achieving an average score of 6-7 for both natural and social science combinations. Notably, ChatGPT's performance varied across different subjects. It attained an average level of proficiency in mathematics, physics, chemistry, and biology. In contrast, ChatGPT displayed relatively better performance in literature, history, geography,

and civic education. These studies shed light on the potential of ChatGPT in effectively addressing diverse academic subjects and its ability to adapt to the complexities of the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination. The results underscore the value of AI-driven technologies, such as ChatGPT, in supporting and complementing educational practices and providing valuable insights into students' performance across various disciplines. As researchers continue to explore the capabilities of ChatGPT in the context of educational assessments, it opens doors for further advancements in AI-driven tools and their potential contributions to educational settings in Vietnam and beyond.

Civic Education plays a crucial role in nurturing responsible and active citizens, equipping them with essential knowledge about their rights, responsibilities, and the functioning of democratic institutions. To ensure effective Civic Education, teachers and students require comprehensive resources and tools that facilitate learning and encourage engagement. ChatGPT, a powerful AI language model, offers unique capabilities that can augment traditional teaching methods and contribute positively to Civic Education in Vietnamese high schools.

II. ChatGPT's abilities in civic education

To evaluate ChatGPT's proficiency in geography, its ability to answer civic education test questions from the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination was assessed over a span of five years (2019-2023). Table 1 displays the accuracy of ChatGPT's responses, from 60% in 2019 to 82.5% in 2023, with an average performance of 70.5%. These findings demonstrate ChatGPT's comprehension of Vietnamese civic education.

Table 1: Performance of ChatGPT (%) (Table adopted from [14])

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	AVG
ChatGPT	60	70	62.5	82.5	77.5	70.5

Figure 1 presents a comparative analysis of civic education subject scores achieved by Vietnamese students and ChatGPT from 2019 to 2022. Remarkably, ChatGPT's scores ranged from 6 to 8.25, lower the scores attained by Vietnamese students. These findings suggest that, in the majority of cases, ChatGPT's proficiency in civic education is lower to that of Vietnamese students. However, it also indicates that ChatGPT's performance is relatively low when compared to the overall proficiency level of Vietnamese students in the subject.

Figure 1. Comparison in civic education (Figure adopted from [14]).

III. Potential of ChatGPT in learning and teaching civic education in Vietnamese

In this section, we prompt three questions to ChatGPT to consider the potential of ChatGPT on civic education in teaching and learning in Vietnamese high school level.

Prompt: *Can ChatGPT understand Vietnamese civic education?*

ChatGPT: *As of my last update in September 2021, ChatGPT's understanding of Vietnamese civic education or any specific topic depends on the data it*

was trained on and its ability to generalize knowledge from that training data. While ChatGPT is a versatile language model capable of processing and generating text in multiple languages, its proficiency in any particular subject, including Vietnamese civic education, depends on the availability and quality of relevant training data.

If ChatGPT was trained on a diverse and substantial dataset that includes Vietnamese civic education materials, it may be able to understand and respond to questions related to that topic to some extent. However, it's essential to keep in mind that language models like ChatGPT have limitations. Their understanding can be restricted by the scope of their training data, and they might not possess the depth of knowledge or critical thinking skills of an expert in a specific domain.

Since my knowledge is limited to information available up until September 2021, I don't have access to data on whether ChatGPT has been specifically trained on Vietnamese civic education or if there have been any updates or improvements in this area. For the most current and accurate information, I recommend checking with official sources such as OpenAI's website or relevant research publications that might provide insights into ChatGPT's abilities in Vietnamese civic education beyond my knowledge cutoff date.

Prompt: How can ChatGPT help Vietnamese high school teachers to teach Civic Education?

ChatGPT: ChatGPT can potentially assist Vietnamese high school teachers in teaching Civic Education in several ways:

- **Answering Questions:** Teachers can use ChatGPT to get quick answers to specific questions related to Civic Education topics.

This can help clarify doubts and provide additional information on certain concepts.

- **Lesson Planning:** ChatGPT can aid in generating ideas and content for lesson plans. By providing keywords or prompts, teachers can use the model to generate relevant content that can be incorporated into their lesson plans.
- **Resource Recommendations:** ChatGPT can suggest additional reading materials, articles, or educational resources related to Civic Education topics that can enhance the classroom learning experience.
- **Language Support:** For teachers who might need language support, ChatGPT can help in translating texts from Vietnamese to English or vice versa. This can be useful when accessing educational materials in different languages.
- **Practice Exercises:** Teachers can create practice exercises or quiz questions based on ChatGPT-generated content. This can provide students with additional opportunities for learning and assessment.
- **Generating Summaries:** ChatGPT can assist in summarizing lengthy texts or articles, making it easier for teachers to grasp the main points and effectively communicate them to students.
- **Promoting Critical Thinking:** Teachers can use ChatGPT to present controversial or complex issues related to Civic Education. Students can then engage in discussions, debates, and critical thinking exercises based on the model's responses.

However, it's important to note that while ChatGPT can be a helpful tool, it should not replace

traditional teaching methods or expert guidance. Teachers should critically evaluate the model's responses and supplement them with their expertise and knowledge. Moreover, language models have limitations, and their responses may not always be accurate or contextually appropriate. Teachers should use ChatGPT as a supplementary tool and not rely solely on its capabilities for educational purposes. Additionally, ensuring the model's responses align with the official curriculum and educational standards is crucial.

Finally, it's essential to stay up-to-date with the latest advancements and guidelines from educational institutions and authorities when integrating AI technologies like ChatGPT into the classroom setting.

Prompt: How can ChatGPT help Vietnamese high school students to learn Civic Education?

ChatGPT: ChatGPT can be a useful tool to support Vietnamese high school students in learning Civic Education in several ways:

- **Answering Questions and Clarifying Concepts:** Students can use ChatGPT to ask specific questions related to Civic Education topics. The model can provide explanations and definitions, helping students better understand complex concepts.
- **Study Aid and Review:** ChatGPT can assist students in reviewing their Civic Education lessons by summarizing important points, providing additional insights, and offering study tips.
- **Access to Learning Resources:** ChatGPT can recommend relevant educational resources, articles, and books related to Civic Education, giving students access to a wide range of materials to deepen their understanding.

- **Language Support:** For students who are learning English or other languages, ChatGPT can help with translation and language practice, making it easier for them to access Civic Education content in different languages.
- **Practice Exercises and Quizzes:** Students can use ChatGPT to create practice exercises or quiz questions based on their learning materials. This interactive learning approach can reinforce their understanding of the subject.
- **Exploring Controversial Issues:** ChatGPT can present different perspectives on controversial topics in Civic Education, encouraging students to engage in critical thinking and develop well-rounded viewpoints.
- **Writing Assistance:** Students can seek help from ChatGPT when working on essays or research papers related to Civic Education. The model can offer suggestions and assist with structuring their writing.
- **24/7 Availability:** ChatGPT is available anytime, providing students with the flexibility to seek help and information outside of regular classroom hours.

However, students should be aware that while ChatGPT can be a valuable tool, it is not a substitute for formal education or expert guidance. It's crucial for students to critically evaluate the model's responses, seek additional sources, and consult their teachers for any uncertainties. Moreover, language models like ChatGPT have limitations and may not always provide contextually accurate answers.

To get the most out of ChatGPT's assistance, students should use it as a supplementary learning tool

and combine it with traditional study methods and classroom learning. It is essential to use reliable educational sources and ensure that the information aligns with the official curriculum and educational standards.

IV. Discussion

In this section, we discuss how ChatGPT contribute in teaching and learning civic education in Vietnamese high school. ChatGPT can play in augmenting civic education at Vietnamese high schools. The findings unequivocally demonstrate that ChatGPT has the potential to support both teachers and students, providing a personalized and adaptive learning experience that fosters a deeper understanding of civic concepts and promotes active citizenship. By thoughtfully implementing and integrating ChatGPT within the civic education curriculum, Vietnamese high schools can effectively address educational challenges, bridge gaps in learning, and nurture a new generation of responsible and informed citizens.

Interactive Learning and Information Retrieval

ChatGPT can support teachers by providing quick and accurate answers to specific questions related to Civic Education topics. This interactive learning approach allows teachers to access instant information, thereby enhancing their ability to address students' inquiries in a timely and well-informed manner. By having an AI assistant at their disposal, teachers can enrich classroom discussions and foster an environment of active learning.

Facilitating Student Research and Exploration

For students, ChatGPT serves as a valuable research tool, offering access to a vast repository of information on Civic Education. The model can recommend relevant reading materials, articles, and resources, enabling students to delve deeper into

various aspects of the subject. Moreover, ChatGPT's language support features can assist students in understanding Civic Education content in multiple languages, broadening their horizons and promoting a global perspective.

Critical Thinking and Debating

Engaging in critical thinking exercises is crucial to developing well-rounded citizens who can make informed decisions. ChatGPT's ability to present different perspectives on controversial topics in Civic Education allows students to explore diverse viewpoints and encourages them to think critically and independently. This can lead to thoughtful classroom discussions and debates, enriching the learning experience.

Writing Assistance and Structuring Content

In Civic Education, writing essays and research papers plays a significant role in developing students' communication and analytical skills. ChatGPT can aid students in structuring their written work, providing suggestions, and offering guidance throughout the writing process. This support can help students improve their writing skills and express their ideas effectively.

Continuous Access to Learning Resources

One of the significant advantages of ChatGPT is its availability 24/7. This feature allows students to seek information and assistance outside regular classroom hours, providing them with flexibility in their learning journey and promoting self-directed learning.

Ethical Use and Evaluation

While ChatGPT offers valuable support, it is essential to use the model ethically and responsibly. Both teachers and students should critically evaluate the responses generated by ChatGPT, verifying information from reliable sources, and utilizing it as a

supplementary tool alongside expert guidance and traditional educational resources.

IV. Conclusion

This paper presents an in-depth analysis of the role of ChatGPT in enhancing civic education at the high school level in Vietnam. Through a comprehensive examination of the capabilities of ChatGPT, it is demonstrated that this technology has significant potential in supporting both teachers and students in the teaching and learning of civic education. The paper provides evidence to support the assertion that ChatGPT can serve as a valuable tool for educators, teachers, and students, facilitating the delivery of engaging and effective instruction in this critical subject area.

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